

SAMPLE-BASED REAL-TIME AUDIO PROCESSING IN MAX/MSP USING SCHEME FOR MAX (S4M)

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ABSTRACT

The audio processing objects in the Max platform operate on fixed-size buffers of audio samples and are executed in a separate audio processing thread from the message handling objects. Implementing audio-processing algorithms typically requires direct access to the individual samples. Currently, the two most common ways of accomplishing this are by writing externals in C or C++, or using the Gen sample-based visual patching environment, which compiles Max objects from visual patches. We describe an alternative approach using an embedded Scheme interpreter executing in the audio thread, allowing direct sample manipulation from a high-level, dynamic language. Scheme code is interpreted at runtime and can be modified interactively while a patch is active and playing. The work is based on the Scheme for Max (S4M) extension to Max, originally developed to operate in either the main or scheduler threads, handling Max messages (rather than audio vectors). Three example use cases are described: spectral processing, audio effects, and audio feature extraction. This enables rapid prototyping of audio processing that can be controlled interactively using the Max patching environment, without requiring a compilation stage or manual memory management from the user, and allowing users to make changes to algorithms without interrupting musical playback.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Max platform (also known as Max/MSP in some earlier versions) has existed for over 30 years, and is widely used by musicians, composers, and computer music developers to create interactive music and multimedia pieces using a visual “low-code” programming paradigm. Max was initially developed as a platform for manipulating messages in real-time, which were then used to control external DSP processors and synthesizers. As processor speed increased, a DSP layer – originally called MSP and provided as an optional extension – was added to the Max platform to provide synchronous data-flow audio processing.

Programs in Max consist of visual containers of audio and message processing objects, each with some number of inlets and outlets that are connected by “wires” to form

“patches”. Interactive systems can be written and controlled by “patching” together these message and audio processing objects. A wide variety of such objects are available to the artist/programmer, both as built-in facilities of the platform and as third-party open-source extensions (called “externals”). The visual data-flow paradigm used by Max enables rapid prototyping and experimentation by users who are not experienced in text-based programming, as well as enabling users who are comfortable in text-languages to mix visual and text programming through objects that embed text languages, such as: the platform’s built-in JavaScript object; externals that host music-specific languages (e.g., Csound, SuperCollider); and externals that host other general-purpose languages, such as Scheme and Lua.

When discussing Max, it is important to differentiate between message handling objects and audio objects. Message handling objects (and the corresponding “wires” that connect their inlets and outlets) are used for processing control data and events. These event messages are passed as lists of atoms, where an atom may be a symbol, number, or string, and passing a message is implemented under the hood as a dynamically dispatched function call handled synchronously by the receiving object. Examples of message-passing objects include **metro**, **bang**, and **route**. Message receiving objects will commonly respond to messages by outputting their own messages out their outlets, for example, executing a mathematical operation on an incoming numerical atom and outputting the sum. However, they may also have side effects on the global environment, such as tempo changes or writing data into global containers such as named audio buffers.

In contrast, audio objects such as **osc~** or **phasor~** that end with the tilde symbol (~) are constantly processing audio buffers that they receive in their inlets and send out their outlets. Conceptually, audio objects are “always on” while processing audio buffers, whereas message objects only “run” when they receive messages. The code in message objects runs in a control-rate thread (either the main/UI thread or the higher-priority scheduler thread) that is separate from the high-priority audio processing thread. The user can determine how many samples are processed in a single pass by setting the *signal vector* size, commonly set to some value between 16 and 128, though when used in the Max for Live environment within Ableton Live, this is locked to 64 samples.

Although visual patching provides varied possibilities and allows rapid prototyping and experimentation, it can be complicated and cumbersome in some scenarios, com-

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pared to text-based programming. Max has addressed this limitation by supporting various types of text-based programming for different purposes. For handling complex event management, control, and arithmetic expressions of messages, Max provides the **js** and **v8** objects that allow the user to run textual code using the JavaScript language directly (v8 providing a more recent JavaScript version, new in Version 9 of Max). The embedded JavaScript interpreter has mechanisms for accessing the inlets and outlets as well as a rich API for interacting with the global environment. However, the JavaScript objects only run in the lower-priority main (a.k.a. UI) thread, meaning that if a user wishes to manipulate sample data, this can only be done in a non-real-time fashion by reading and writing to audio buffers.

Audio processing in Max is computed in fixed-size buffers of audio samples. Many audio processing algorithms require low-level access to individual samples of a buffer. Max can be extended with new objects (message or audio) by compiling externals using the C or C++ programming languages, based on template code provided in the Max software development kit (SDK). Externals are dynamically loaded by the platform, allowing advanced users and programmers to create their own objects which take advantage of the faster computation and low-level access to individual samples provided by C/C++.

Another more recent alternative for low-level access to individual samples in Max is the **Gen** environment, which provides a visual patching paradigm similar to Max patching, in which the user graphically connects primitives to form audio processing algorithms that operate sample by sample. Gen visual patches are compiled when saved, creating efficient code and enabling the resulting (compiled) audio object to be loaded in the associated **gen~** object, and then used like any other audio object in Max, as well as exported to other environments. Gen patches may also be created using Gen textual code, a very minimal, C-like language for DSP manipulation.

Scheme for Max (S4M)¹ is an open-source extension to Max that enables scripting, live coding, and algorithmic music creation within Max using text-based programming in the Scheme programming language. It can reasonably be summed up as an alternative to the **js** JavaScript object. However, unlike the **js** and **v8** objects, S4M can be used for timing critical tasks, as it can be run in either the high-priority scheduler thread or the main/UI thread. Another advantage over JavaScript is that the source code of Scheme can be more easily manipulated as data, including as Max messages themselves, which significantly simplifies the creation of mixed visual and code patches, and allows code to be easily generated and passed around dynamically (e.g. a Scheme definition can be updated during playback by sending a block of code from a text editor to the Max environment via Open Sound Control messages transmitted over a local UDP connection). Finally, there are clear correspondences between the Max message and Scheme syntaxes that makes interfacing the two systems

easier (e.g., a Max message may easily be constructed that contains a valid Scheme s-expression, including the use of Max's messages interpolation facilities).

In this paper, we describe how we have extended the Scheme for Max project by adding an audio-rate **s4m~** object that can generate or transform audio vectors by executing audio-processing algorithms in the audio processing thread, while simultaneously receiving Max event messages in the main and scheduler threads. This enables low-level sample operations in a high-level, memory-managed language, with the ability to update definitions and code interactively on the fly, rather than requiring compilation, as is necessary with Gen objects or C/C++ externals. Of particular interest to composers is that these updates can even be done in such a manner as to preserve program state, allowing composer-programmers to experiment with low-level changes to audio algorithms without needing to restart a musical piece or reload its data.

To illustrate the potential, challenges, and advantages of our proposed approach, we describe three use cases: 1) time-domain audio processing; 2) frequency-domain audio processing; and 3) audio feature extraction. These examples illustrate how various types of low-level sample-based audio processing can be performed in real time using S4M.

2. RELATED WORK

Max/MSP [1] and PureData [2] are arguably the most widely used visual programming frameworks for interactive audio, computer music, and multimedia processing. There are also many text-based programming frameworks for computer music, such as Csound [3], Supercollider [4], Nyquist [5], and ChuckK [6]. All these programming languages for computer music use ideas and concepts that were introduced by the venerable family of MUSIC X languages originally designed and implemented by Max Matthews in the early days of computer music [7], including unit generators; visual patching; and separate audio and control rates. The majority of computer music languages operate on fixed-size buffers of audio samples, though some more recent languages, such as ChuckK, operate directly on individual audio samples.

S4M uses s7 Scheme, an embeddable Scheme Lisp [8] implementation by Bill Schottstaedt at CCRMA. Among text-based extensions for Max, S4M is unique in that it is capable of running in the Max scheduler thread, allowing functions to be executed with the same temporal accuracy as any other (non-audio) Max event, such as MIDI or metronome output [9]. There is also a version for Pure Data [10], and S4M may be run inside the Ableton Live digital audio workstation through the Max for Live extension, in which context the scheduling accuracy allows its use alongside commercial sequencing tools with the same level of timing and synchronization accuracy as other Max for Live objects.

There is a long tradition of computer music languages and platforms built on top of the Scheme and Lisp family of languages, including the **Common Music** [11] environment, which also uses s7 Scheme as its underlying language. Another example of such a computer music lan-

¹ <https://github.com/iainctduncan/scheme-for-max/>

guage based on Lisp is **Nyquist**, by Roger Dannenberg [5]. Nyquist does not have separate notions of control and audio rate signals and allows for low-level audio processing of individual samples. **Common Lisp Music** [12] is yet another Lisp-based programming library used for generating music scores and algorithmic composition, created by the author of *s7*, but predating it.

With regard to sample-level programming, the **ChuckK** [6] language naturally supports concurrency and precise timing, and operates on individual samples. However, this timing precision comes at the expense of higher computational requirements than the more traditional buffer-based computer music languages. Gen [13] similarly operates at the sample level, but is compiled to code that can be executed efficiently.

Time-domain audio processing is based on processing arrays of audio samples to perform various types of digital signal processing (DSP) effects such as filtering (low-pass, band-pass, high-pass), compression, and reverb [14]. An excellent introduction to these concepts is *The Digital Signal Processing Primer* [15].

Frequency-domain or spectral processing refers to transformation of audio signals to a frequency domain, typically through the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), where they are manipulated or analyzed, and possibly transformed back to the time domain. A detailed description of spectral processing in Max can be found in third volume of Cipriani and Giri [16].

Music Information Retrieval (MIR) [17] algorithms extract various types of information from music audio signals. There are dedicated libraries and frameworks for MIR, such as **Marsyas** [18] and **librosa** [19], but there is also work in extending computer music languages with MIR functionality. For example, PureData has been extended with timbre classification [20] and ChuckK with real-time MIR prototyping [21].

3. AUDIO PROCESSING IN SCHEME FOR MAX

This paper describes a new addition to the Scheme for Max family, the **s4m~** object. In order to enable processing audio samples safely in Max using *s7* Scheme, the *s7* interpreter must execute in the DSP rendering thread alone. While *s7* is thread-safe, it supports only a single Scheme thread. That is to say, we may safely run many *s7* interpreters in one Max patch, and may concurrently run separate *s7* interpreters in separate threads (e.g, a separate S4M instance handling UI events and scheduling events), but it is not guaranteed to be safe to run Scheme operations from multiple threads using the same *s7* interpreter instance. Thus, to prevent potential crashes from the *s7* garbage collector being triggered from another thread, we limit all *s7* access to the code executing in only the Max DSP thread.

To make this possible, a completely separate audio-only version of S4M was implemented from distinct C-code. In the **s4m~** object, all Scheme code evaluations (i.e., all calls to the *s7* interpreter to evaluate an expression) are run in the Max audio rendering callback, executing once per audio-vector of samples.

3.1 Thread safety and queuing

However, in Max, we must be able to pass event messages to objects to enable them to do much that is useful (i.e., to have them respond to actions taken in the rest of the patch, such as MIDI input, scheduled events, and GUI interactions). In the regular **s4m** object (and similarly in the built in JavaScript objects) this is handled by having incoming messages from other threads implicitly queued and safely dequeued by the receiving object using some form of thread-safe queue. Similarly, in the **s4m~** object, Max messages are received in inlet zero, and then passed over a queue to the code that will act on them from the audio callback.

In this first version of **s4m~**, the queue for incoming event messages is implemented using a Max audio buffer object as the data container, chosen as a simple prototyping method because the Max buffer object provides the built-in ability to lock buffer data for safe sharing between Max message and audio threads.

When event messages of Max atoms are received in inlet zero of the **s4m~** object, they are translated to pure strings and stored in a dedicated buffer (a hidden instance of a Max **buffer** object), along with some message metadata, such as the message number on the queue. On every audio render pass (once per signal vector of samples), the **s4m~** object's audio callback code checks the buffer for incoming messages, and if any are received, these are dequeued and evaluated in the Scheme interpreter using the *s7* FFI functions for evaluating C strings. While not the most robust possible solution (i.e., a user could conceivably clobber the queue by using the same buffer for some other purpose), this has proven safe and has been adequate for verifying that the system works and is worthy of further development effort.

3.2 Thread safety limitations

In Max, a common workflow is that a user creates an object with some starting arguments, in some cases triggering various initialization processes at object creation time. For example, one may provide a file name to the **js** object, which will result in the file being read from the file system and evaluated in the interpreter. The Max user may elect to create objects while their patch is dormant, in which case slow operations are not a problem, or may do so while their patch is playing. Max makes no promises of real-time safety in this regard — one may easily create audio dropouts if one decides to alter the Max patch in ways that result in too much work for the system to execute without missing the deadline for the calculation of an audio buffer of samples.

In the **s4m~** object, the initialization of the *s7* Scheme interpreter happens at the time of object creation, which executes in the main thread. If one provides a file name to the object, this work includes reading the file contents from the file system and evaluating these as an initial bootstrapping Scheme program for the object. At present, this means that using **s4m~** does require some care on the part of the user, in that there is nothing preventing a user from

instantiating objects in a Max patcher while DSP processing is running, which could cause concurrency issues if a thread switch to the DSP thread happens before object initialization is complete. Users are thus advised to pause audio rendering while creating objects – or accept that once in a while this might cause a crash.

Similarly, if the user is loading a large Scheme program, the work entailed to do so may cause a missed deadline for the Max audio thread. Whether this is the case will depend on the latency with which the user is running Max (controlled by the hardware buffer size and signal vector size preferences) and the amount of code and work involved in the bootstrapping program. This requires some care (and decision making) on the part of the user, but this type of scenario is common with many Max objects and programs and is not considered onerous or unacceptable by a typical Max user (e.g., one can similarly miss a deadline by writing or reading a large enough block of audio samples into a buffer from the scheduler thread).

We hope to provide more robust protections in future (such as preventing initialization if DSP rendering is not turned off), however, we feel the requirement to stop audio processing while creating new `s4m~` objects is not onerous, especially as the Max platform does not perfectly support audio rendering while changing patches anyway (i.e., unlike some other computer music languages such as SuperCollider and Csound, one cannot change the DSP graph during playback without potentially incurring audio dropouts).

3.3 Stability

The design used works adequately and safely, enabling the execution of arbitrary Scheme code, including function re-definition, while audio processing is running (e.g., from code sent in over the local network).

Stability was verified using load testing patches that send unrealistically high volumes of Scheme evaluation calls to the object during audio rendering, with the load-testing patch using randomization of the time interval between calls. This load test patch has been run successfully for over an hour of processing without issue (hundreds of thousands of calls), with periods of around 10 ms between messages.

Figure 1 shows the patch used to stress test the audio processing with Max messages. This gives a strong indication that the potential threading issues with message passing to the audio processing object have been addressed adequately with the queue system.

3.4 Performance and Garbage Collection

Of course, it is possible for a user to tax the interpreter beyond what is feasible within processing time limits, and this is rendered more complex by the fact that the interpreter must occasionally run its garbage collector (GC). The `s7` garbage collector is a straightforward mark-and-sweep collector, thus entailing some “stop-the-world” pauses. While one might assume this will cause insurmountable issues in an audio environment, this is not the case for several reasons.

Figure 1. Stress testing sending messages to S4M audio

First, the target user for this project is the composer-programmer who wishes to interact with algorithms in real-time while working on a composition or media piece. That is to say, it is not intended to provide a platform on which one will develop a large program intended for commercial distribution to naive users. It is thus most likely that the programs being run are very small – a user could certainly make something large, but for the project to be *useful*, this is not necessary, and a more likely scenario is that it is used in one component of many in a larger Max patch. The `s7` interpreter preallocates the heap and runs the collector when the heap approaches exhaustion (or on demand), sweeping the heap. If the user’s program is small, sweeping the heap is very fast, usually under a few (or even one) ms (`s7` provides facilities for inspecting GC run times). While this may at first blush seem like an unacceptable pause time for audio generation, in fact, a user working with real-time audio on the Mac or Windows operating systems is already used to having to run with significant system latency to compensate for CPU spikes. For example, one of the authors has found that with or without S4M running, using Max for Live in the context of the Ableton Live DAW, along with various heavy-load commercial VST plugins, he is commonly faced with having to run a 256 sample hardware buffer to prevent audio dropouts. In this context, the additional stop-the-world pause must only fit within this 6ms ongoing head-room buffer (256 samples at 44100 samples per second), which is in addition to the time period given the audio vector size (i.e., one really has 256 samples plus 64 samples when running with a 64 sample vector, as is the case by default in Ableton Live).

Users accustomed to running heavy commercial plugins (e.g., U-He’s Diva, VCV Rack, or similar) are already used to the fact that prominent musical times (downbeats) may produce CPU spikes requiring running at high latency. While it is true that adding S4M (and the resultant GC pause) to this equation may require the user to “up the latency a notch”, we feel this is a tradeoff that many composer-programmers will be happy to make, given the interactivity and productivity gains offered by enabling the use of a high-level, memory-managed language with

a real-time REPL. This is certain the case for the authors, who are capable of writing extensions in C, but would prefer to interactively code during playback whenever possible, without the possibility of a crash from an out-of-bounds error.

Secondly, the savvy user may avoid creating much work for the GC at a code level. The implementation of `s4m~` already reuses statically allocated arrays for passing the block of samples in and out of Scheme-space. Users can likewise reuse globally allocated vectors in Scheme should they desire, allowing them to avoid allocating memory on every audio pass (i.e., they can avoid creating new cons-cells or otherwise allocating on the heap on each audio vector render).

Thirdly, `s7` offers some controls over the GC to the user. For example, one can disable the GC and then run it on demand from Scheme code, allowing the advanced user to trigger the GC in less busy moments (i.e., between sixteenth notes, which will be 100 to 200 ms apart at standard tempos). Or one can even disable the GC entirely for the duration of a piece, perhaps allocating a larger heap as necessary to do so. While these measures may seem extreme or hacky to someone unfamiliar with audio production, such practices are not uncommon amongst computer music producers who have been coming up with unorthodox ways to squeeze out performance for decades, and who are used to provisioning systems around gigabytes of audio samples.

Finally, as detailed below, one of the use cases most likely to arouse interest is that of spectral processing. In this context, the processing only needs to run once per FFT frame hop size (i.e., each time a frame of samples is ready). In this case, the user is granted additional temporal room should they choose a large hopsize (though of course this comes at the cost of latency).

As the `s7` GC is not tailored for soft-real time use (optimizing for small pause times), as is the case for example with Roger Dannenberg's Serpent language, there is certainly room for improvements (and some are planned, as detailed in future work). But the result of the authors' tests is that the system, as is, enables musical work in a way that is sufficiently convenient and different from available options to be a worthwhile addition, and performs adequately under constraints that are not considered too severe by modern computer music production standards.

4. USE CASES

In this section, we provide some examples of how the `s4m~` object can be used for sample-level audio processing. While simple, these are representative of the type of audio processing one might wish to perform, and help illustrate different aspects of the system and its integration with the graphical patch environment of Max.

4.1 Time-Domain Audio Processing

The simplest digital filter is arguably a two-sample averaging filter in which the output at sample n is calculated as the average of the current input sample and the previous in-

put sample. This is an example of a simple Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filter described by the following equation:

$$y[n] = \frac{x[n-1] + x[n]}{2} \quad (1)$$

The code below shows how this simple filter can be implemented in Scheme. On each audio processing pass, the `perform` function will be called by the host, passing in an integer argument, `frames`, that corresponds to the number of samples per process block, determined by the audio vector size setting. In each `perform` call, we read input samples from the statically allocated global float vectors `in-l` and `in-r`, and write to the similarly allocated output vectors `out-l` and `out-r`. These vectors of floating point samples are created statically by C code in the `s4m~` implementation through the `s7` foreign function interface (FFI), and are accessed directly without requiring any memory copying or allocation. They are each of length `frames`, and are protected from garbage collection.

Additionally, in this algorithm we need to preserve some state between between calls to the processing passes to store the previous output sample, thus there are two Scheme-space global variables, `prev-l` and `prev-r`. Extending the code to handle arbitrary Finite Impulse Response (FIR) and Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filters is straightforward by using global variables to hold the previous input and output samples needed between calls to the `perform` function. (Note that, as `s7` is reentrant and thread-safe, "global" means the variable is only global to the particular `s4m~` instance in use, having no effect on any other `s4m~` objects.)

Listing 1. 'Simple Filter'

```
; hold last sample from previous buffer
(define prev-l 0.0)
(define prev-r 0.0)

(define (perform frames)
  ; loop over the samples in a frame
  (do ((i 0 (+ 1 i)) ((>= i frames))
      ; read from input vectors
      (let* ((sig-l (float-vector-ref in-l i))
            (sig-r (float-vector-ref in-r i))
            ; do the filtering
            (filt-l (/ (+ sig-l prev-l) 2))
            (filt-r (/ (+ sig-r prev-r) 2)))
          ; write to the output vectors
          (float-vector-set! out-l i filt-l)
          (float-vector-set! out-r i filt-r)
          ; update state variables for next pass
          (set! prev-l filt-l)
          (set! prev-r filt-r))))
```

This code can be saved as a file on the Max search path and the filename used as an argument to the `s4m~` object in a Max patch, resulting in the file loading at object creation time and the `perform` function being called repeatedly as long as DSP processing is enabled in Max.

4.2 Frequency-Domain Audio Processing

Frequency-domain processing is commonly performed by overlapping fixed segments of the audio signal, multiplying them by a window function, and then performing the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to convert them to a frequency representation consisting of pairs of complex numbers. These complex numbers can be converted to a pair of

Figure 2. Patch and subpatch for overlap-add short-time Fourier Transform spectral processing using S4M.

floating point numbers representing magnitude and phase. A variety of manipulations and transformations can be applied using this frequency or spectral representation. Following the spectral calculations, the magnitude and phase values can be converted back to complex numbers with real and imaginary parts, and then transformed back to the time domain using the inverse FFT. The Max platform provides built-in objects for Fourier analysis and resynthesis (**pfft~**, **fftin~**, and **fftout~**) as well as helper objects for converting complex number pairs to and from magnitude and phase pairs (**cartopol~** and **poltocar~**). By using these Max objects before and after the **s4m~** object, we can have the Scheme code work only on magnitude and phase values.

Figure 2 shows how the **s4m~** object can be embedded in a Max subpatch that performs spectral processing on audio buffers. Listing 2 shows the corresponding Scheme code. The windowing and overlap-and-add process is handled by the **pfft~** object in the parent patch. In this example, we also illustrate sending control arguments to Scheme through Max event messages. Max message interpolation is used to create s-expressions to update the Scheme variables **vol** and **bin**, which are evaluated by the interpreter as part of the audio processing block after queuing and dequeuing. In this example, these are used to set the bin number above which bin amplitudes are changed, and the amount by which the bin volumes are changed. Note that the left channel contains the real part of the spectrum and the right channel contains the imaginary part. Although this example is simple for brevity it is straightforward to extend to more complicated spectral processing, such as making a voice sound robotic, with similar computational requirements.

Notice that arbitrary Scheme code can be sent directly from the Max patcher as a message to the **s4m~**. This

is a core feature of S4M, and this ability to send Scheme code as messages affords various possibilities for live coding and on-the-fly prototyping, providing flexibility and interactivity beyond what is possible in compiled approaches such as C/C++ externals or Gen. For example, one could reconstruct the Max patch components that create the s-expressions on the fly, changing how Scheme is used to control these variables, all without interrupting audio playback.

Listing 2. Spectral Processing

```
; globals that get set from outside using Scheme
; code in Max messages
(define vol 0.0)
(define bin 4)

(define (perform frames)
  ; loop over samples
  (do ((i 0 (+ 1 i))) ((>= i frames))
    ; set volumes below and above bin
    (let ((bin-vol (if (= i bin) vol 0.0))
          (sig-l (float-vector-ref in-l i))
          (sig-r (float-vector-ref in-r i)))
      ; change magnitude output
      (float-vector-set! out-l i (* sig-l
                                   bin-vol))
      ; set phase to 0
      (float-vector-set! out-r i 0.0))))
```

In our tests on an M1 Mac Mini, we were able to dynamically update the control variables in real-time, and did not experience any audio dropouts. Although relatively simple, this type of spectral processing is an example of an algorithm that is significantly more cumbersome to program purely graphically in Max.

4.3 Audio Feature Extraction

The final example demonstrates computing the spectral centroid from the magnitude spectrum of a signal, a task common in music information retrieval. In this example, the centroid is simply posted to the Max console by the S4M **post** function. Subsequent versions of **s4m~** will include an output queue mechanism to enable using this value in the rest of a Max patch by sending output messages from **s4m~**. We feel the flexibility and the interactive possibilities this will afford will have the potential to be valuable additions to the ways one can conduct MIR with Max, and open up interesting possibilities for prototyping and interaction that are impossible or impractical with existing systems [21].

The spectral centroid is defined as follows:

$$C = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} f_k \cdot |X(k)|}{\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |X(k)|} \quad (2)$$

where $|X(k)|$ is the magnitude spectrum at frequency bin k and f_k is the frequency corresponding to bin k .

Listing 3 contains the Scheme code for computing the spectral centroid, receiving as input the magnitude and phase spectrum for the left and right audio buffer. The first loop calculates the sum of the magnitude values for normalizing the magnitude spectrum, and the second loop accumulates the dot-product calculation needed for computing the centroid. More complex audio features such as

Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) or Chroma could be computed in a similar manner with additional code.

Listing 3. Audio Feature Extraction

```
(define (perform frames)
  (let ((sum 0.0001)
        (centroid 0.00001))

    (do ((i 0 (+ 1 i))) ((>= i frames))
      (let* ((sig-l (float-vector-ref in-l i))
             (set! sum (+ sum sig-l))))

      (do ((i 0 (+ 1 i))) ((>= i frames))
        (let* ((sig-l (float-vector-ref in-l i))
               (set! centroid (+ centroid (* i (/ sig-l
                                                    sum))))))

          (set! centroid (/ centroid frames))
          (post " - detected centroid:" centroid)))
```

5. SUMMARY AND FUTURE WORK

We have shown that Scheme for Max can be used in the audio processing thread of the Max environment to perform real-time, low-level audio processing with access to individual audio samples. This enables a variety of interesting possibilities for prototyping and experimentation that can be performed dynamically without requiring recompilation. The text-based S4M code is straightforward to use within the visual patching environment of Max and allows interactive exploration and debugging while audio playback continues.

In the future, we intend to implement a library of helpful – and more complex – processing functions for digital audio effects, spectral processing, and music information retrieval. We also intend to provide additional input and output facilities, such as are included in the main `s4m` object (e.g. sending Max messages, writing to named buffers and dictionaries). We believe that more sophisticated algorithms to perform more complex audio processing tasks (such as convolution-based cross-synthesis, monophonic pitch detection, autotuning, beat tracking, and audio classification) will be possible to implement in Scheme, and given our experiments and tests, should be possible to run in real time on modern computers.

Other potential areas of work include: integration with other computer music environments; creating a version for PureData; and optimizing the `s7` garbage collector for low pause times, as has been done in Dannenberg’s Serpent computer music programming language [22].

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